

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

FORMATION OF LINGUOCULTURAL COMPETENCE USING AUTHENTIC VIDEO CONTENT

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Abstract

The article presents the features of the use of video materials in a foreign language lesson as part of a linguistic research undertaken as part of the professional training of an English teacher. This article reflects the methodological aspects of training teachers to work with video material in order to diversify the traditional form of work through the introduction of authentic materials. The article describes the use of video materials, which activates the attention and arouses the interest of students in a foreign language, touches upon the issue of choosing authentic video materials and the effectiveness of their use in the classroom. In this paper, an innovative method of teaching with the help of video will be studied, and methodological recommendations will be given for the use of video content. This article provides an example of working on English-language video material.

Keywords: Authentic video content, criteria for choosing an authentic video material, self-motivation, teaching foreign languages, video recordings, authentic video material, authentic documents, innovative technologies, video programs for studying

INTRODUCTION

The formation of linguocultural competence is the main and leading goal of foreign language education. This is especially true today.

At the same time, in the process of mastering foreign language communication, it is very important to focus on the development of the ability to perceive foreign speech by ear. In addition, it should be remembered that language is closely related to culture. Today, when special attention is paid to the use of innovative technologies in the learning process, the use of video materials in the classroom, which is one of the types of such technologies, is a natural and correct approach to teaching. Due to the fact that this method is still gaining popularity, it is unusual, non-trivial and interesting for students, as it helps to assimilate information through authentic video materials, immersing themselves in the socio-cultural and linguistic environment in the classroom.[1]

Some believe that the use of video in the classroom is unnecessary, it scatters the attention of students. However, in this work it is necessary to refute this fact and consider the importance of video materials as one of the means that increase the activity of students

in the classroom and give rise to their desire to speak out, to express their opinion about what they see.

I- THE USE OF AUTHENTIC VIDEO CONTENT

The use of video recordings in English lessons contributes to the individualization of learning and the development of motivation for the speech activity of students. The specificity of video materials as a means of teaching a foreign language provides communication with real objects that stimulate almost genuine communication: students seem to become participants in all situations played out with their help, play certain roles, solve "real", life problems. The resulting effect of participation in the daily life of the country of the language being studied not only contributes to learning a natural, living language, but also serves as a powerful incentive to increase students' motivation.

Currently, a lot of information, materials, adapted authentic films are offered with ready-made developments. The teacher has the opportunity to select material and show it in class. However, such lessons do not always bring results and are not effective.

Choose the right video to show, but in what sequence to offer tasks to students?

The use of video contributes to the development of various types of mental activity, primarily attention and memory. During viewing in the classroom, an atmosphere of joint cognitive activity arises. Under these conditions, even an inattentive student becomes attentive. In order to understand the content of the film,

students need to make some effort. So involuntary attention turns into arbitrary. And the intensity of attention affects the process of memorization. Use of various channels of information receipt (auditory, visual, motor perception) has a positive effect on the

strength of imprinting regional and linguistic material.[2]

The use of video in a foreign language lesson should always be more than a symbolic trip to the cinema or watching a TV show. While watching the video, the teacher comments on certain points, and then the students share their impressions of what they saw.

II - THE CHOICE OF AUTHENTIC VIDEO CONTENT

1. Main criteria for selecting authentic video materials

Video is an excellent supplementary material for learning English, as it is as close to language reality as possible. The video contains visual images and the necessary audio material, which makes the memorization process efficient and easy. Video can be used in the lesson to familiarize and study new material, as well as for repetition. [3]

In order to choose the right authentic video materials, we need to understand what categories are important when choosing, what factors affect effectiveness, and what teacher requirements should be demanded to prepare a lesson with this type of material.

First of all, the criteria for choosing an authentic video material are many and varied. It is necessary to take into account the elements that arouse motivation in the learning of any language in the learner. These

elements must be compatible with the needs of the learners.[4] Here it is up to the teacher to seek out, choose and finally offer the material used to teach the socio-cultural realities of the language studied. An authentic video material must be adapted to the public, it must interest and motivate it. A document must be found where the communication situation must appear clearly. That is to say, the nature of the document, speakers, place, time of the interaction, how the interaction takes place, cause, issue of the interaction. The video must be pedagogically usable. The communicative content must be relevant to the progression, so it must be in line with the targeted communicative objectives.

These elements are a few aspects that can promote the pleasure of learning for learners. Authentic video material is chosen to adapt it to the context, age and language level of the learners.

2. Audience

Focusing on his own audience, the teacher, in addition to the level, must of course take into account the age characteristics of the learners. It is necessary to take an interest in the various needs of the latter in order to succeed in teaching.

Students of different age groups have a number of psycho-physiological characteristics that must be taken into account in lessons of foreign languages. [5]

Age	Use of video content
5-10	In the classes, it is important to present the authentic video material, as well as the frequent change of activities. It is especially important to activate the main channels of perception and create positive motivation in children with the help of games.
11-17	In the classrooms, the role of analysis, generalization, systematization and repetition of video material is reinforced. The lessons create conditions in which each student has the opportunity to prove themselves.
18-25	In classes, it is effective to use role-playing, discussions, problematic orientation games, project methods, collaborative training using videos and cognitive materials. The classroom teacher becomes a communication partner, an Assistant, guiding the learning process.[6]
26+	The teacher should involve students at all stages of the educational process, use various games and techniques that improve and facilitate the memorization of material and allow you to immediately begin to apply the knowledge acquired in life.

CONCLUSION

Based on the data of the article, it can be concluded that at the moment there is no ideally developed methodology for teaching a foreign language using technical textbooks, and in particular video programs. Nevertheless, this method is being introduced into the educational process with great speed and contributes to the development of linguocultural competence within the framework of modern foreign language education.

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